

We have been observing chromosome preparations of root tips and pollen mother cells to determine the chromosome number of IRG wild rice accessions. To date, 742 accessions representing 18 wild *Oryza* species have been cytologically examined. Our observations (see table) revealed that, in general, chromosome numbers in the wild *Oryza* species were constantly $2n=2x=24$ in the diploid species *O. australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. granulata*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. nivara*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*, and in the majority of *O. eichingeri* and *O. officinalis* accessions. They were

$2n=4x=48$ in the tetraploid species *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, *O. longiglumis*, *O. minuta*, *O. punctata*, and *O. ridleyi*. Unexpected chromosome numbers were observed in *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri*. In a total of 138 *O. officinalis* accessions, 136 were found to be diploid ($2n=24$), but two accessions from India were tetraploid ($2n=48$). Our examination also showed that four accessions (out of 18) originally identified as *O. eichingeri*, from Uganda and Sri Lanka, had 48 chromosomes in the root-tip cells. Considering that both *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri* should be purely diploid species, the correct iden-

tification of the $4x$ forms must be confirmed. On the other hand, this observation also indicated the possible existence of two different cytological types of *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri*.

In addition, a low frequency of aneuploid cells with chromosome numbers varying between 20 and 26 were found in a few accessions of *O. australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. granulata*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. nivara*, and diploid *O. officinalis*. A low number of tetraploid cells with 48 chromosomes was also observed in two *O. nivara* accessions and six *O. officinalis* accessions. ■

Genetics

Genetics of protein per grain in rice

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Seed protein content is usually expressed as percent brown (dehulled) rice protein (BRP). This trait is highly influenced by environment and, hence, its expression is complex. It has been suggested that instead of considering BRP, it would be effective to use as selection criterion the actual protein

Analysis of variance for combining ability. Tamil Nadu, India. 1993 DS.

Source	df	Mean squares	F
GCA	5	0.71**	61.89
SCA	15	0.08**	7.38
Reciprocal	15	0.24**	20.70
Error	70	0.01	0.001
σ^2g	0.06		
σ^2s	0.07		
σ^2A	0.12		
σ^2D	0.07		
Predictability ratio			

$$\frac{2\sigma^2g}{2\sigma^2g + \sigma^2s} = 0.63$$

σ^2g = genetic component due to GCA

σ^2s = genetic component due to SCA

σ^2A = additive variance ($2\sigma^2g$)

σ^2D = dominance variance (σ^2s)

available per grain (PPG) since the latter is less influenced by environment. However, information on inheritance patterns of PPG in rice is scanty.

We studied gene action and estimated general combining ability (GCA) using six parents (IR50, ADT37, ADT41, Duansan, TKM6, and ADT39) and 30 hybrids generated through full diallel mating.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1993 dry season. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in three rows of 3 m length and in 30×20 -cm spacing in a field fertilized with 120 kg N ha^{-1} , $26.4 \text{ kg P ha}^{-1}$, and $49.8 \text{ kg K ha}^{-1}$. Observations were recorded for five randomly selected plants per replication.

A total of 100 fully filled, healthy grains from each plant were randomly sorted out and their weights recorded. Ten grains were taken randomly, dehulled manually, and ground to fine powder. Each sample was analyzed by the standard micro-Kjeldahl method to obtain %N. The BRP content was derived by multiplying %N by 5.95. The PPG (mg) was estimated as $[\%BRP \times 100\text{-grain weight (g)} \times 10]$.

The analysis of variance for GCA clearly indicated the importance of

both additive and nonadditive genetic variance (see table). The higher values (>0.5) of predictability ratios also revealed the preponderance of additive genetic variance. The additive genetic variance could be effectively used by simple pedigree method of breeding.

Among the six parents, IR50, ADT37, and ADT41 were found to be the best, and they could be used in hybridization programs to improve PPG. ■

The relationship between the morphological fertility of pollen and marker gene *Est 9*

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Many indica-japonica hybrids exhibit a low seed set. In cases where female gamete fertility is normal, the lowered seed set can be attributed to pollen sterility. To use the strong heterosis of indica-japonica hybrids, we must overcome the barrier of pollen sterility.

We analyzed genes for pollen hybrid sterility in F_2 populations from three-way crosses of Akihikari //IR36/